

THEORETICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODERN PROJECT OF THE FOOTBALL HALL BUILDING

Shirzad Karima¹, Turayev Khumoyiddin Abdugafforovich²

¹ Magistrate of Engineering Graphics and Design Theory, Termez State University

² Scientific consultant, Termez State University

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ABSTRACT

This article gives theoretical recommendations on the implementation of the modern project of the Football Hall building

Sports facilities - a separate building for recreation, training and various sports competitions, and a complex of construction sports facilities represent modern sports facilities. It can be said that the orchestra in the city of Olympia and Gymnasium, Stadium, hippopotamus, circus etc. In Amphitheater and colliiefs in Rome, the stadium and combined. By the 19th century, the construction of sports facilities accelerated. Artificial ponds were created (1820-30), gymnastic halls (1850) CAD. repeated styling in the form.

The restoration of the Olympiad games from 1896 year gave an opportunity to increase the construction of sports facilities. By the 20th century, sports facilities were enriched with new modern architectural styles based on national architectural traditions of each state. These are Rome (1960), Tokyo (1964), Munich (1972), Moscow (1980), Seoul (1988), Atlanta (1996), Sydney (2000) and other Olympiad complexes designed specifically: the largest Olympiad in Japan (Tokyo) Ioyogi Stadium (1964, architect K. Tange, engineer I. Subon) is one of the best works of modern Japanese architecture. The use of hanging

structures in the building has a high efficiency, creating an opportunity for the creation of new plastic. Modern sports facilities serve about 50 types of sports. The main construction consists of an area where exercises and competitions are held, a hall and auxiliary rooms (a wardrobe, a shower, a judge's room, a room where sports equipment is stored, etc.).

The complex of sports facilities includes technical use of engineering equipment (electricity, water, sewerage, ventilation), device facilities for spectators (stands, foyer, buffet, sanuzel, etc.). Also, sports facilities are built both indoor and Outdoor (according to the request of the training), mulched for one or more sports (for example, gyms for gymnastics and other sports games universal halls), as well as specialized sports complexes for different types of Sports located in the general territory (for example, outdoor sports facilities; football, athletics, skiing sport, trampoline, cycling and other, indoor sports facilities;

artistic gymnastics, waterslide, kort, skating sport and others).¹

For the purpose of year-round use of the modern Si, magnificent facilities began to be built, which were transformed from one form to another (open in summer, closed in winter) [the International Iokogama Stadium in Japan (1997, 72 370 seats), the stat de Frans Stadium in Senden (1999, 80 000 seats, in which light athletics and rugby games are held. Seats can be increased or reduced with the help of special engineering devices), Sydney "Australia" Stadium (1999, 80 000 seats, Area 1 to 16, roof 30 000 sq m, project in the form of an Australian National hat), Seoul "Syangam" Stadium (2001, 64 677 seats, Tribune Hill built in the form of a sailing boat of local fishermen), trousers.

New Wembley Stadium in west London (construction 2003 y. I started, 90 000 seats, architect Norman Foster, with the help of computer technology, designed the roof in the form of Silge, open in the summer, closed in the winter) and other].

In Uzbekistan 60-80y.projects of sports facilities in the city were carried out on the basis of state order [named after Mitrofanov in Tashkent (1963), "dolphin" in Navoi (1965) ponds, Pakhtakor Stadium and other]. After independence, special attention is paid to physical education and sports, the construction of sports facilities. The construction of stadiums, gyms, sports fields is being intensively carried out.

The sports facilities under construction make it possible to hold high-level international competitions (Yunusabad tennis court and water basin, 1996; Central Stadium" Tashlak "in Ferghana, 1996; Sports Complex" Jar", 1998; tennis court" Karshi", 1998; Termiz Wrestling Complex; 1999; Sports Complex

"Humo" (1999) and "Buxoro" in Bukhara, 2002; Sports Complex "youth" in Namangan, 2003; Sports college "Olympic reserves" in Andijan, 2003; swimming complex" dolphin " in Termiz, 2003 and others).

Sports pavilions are designed to serve throughout the year, including outdoor sports grounds and stadium facilities, outdoor ponds, yachts, rowing stations, sniper stands, as well as playgrounds for various sports (volleyball, basketball, tennis, etc.).

According to the objectives of the Pavilions, the rooms, the squares are also of type. Therefore, the compositional methods of planning them have a different character. The Sports Pavilion in a simple composition has a rectangular tarpaulin, with a common single entrance for women and men from the frontal or side of the building. When designing pavilions, it is necessary to provide a convenient schedule of movement for them, taking into account the division of the flow of athletes using the vestibule and moving towards the gym.

In order to facilitate the service of all outdoor sports fields and playgrounds in a stadium of small or medium size, it is desirable that the sports pavilion is located in the center. For small sports pavilions, the following system of rooms is provided: a vestibule (with a wardrobe), a storage room, a room for providing and presenting a skylights, a buffet, a sanitary-hygiene room, a room for sports equipment; a gym, with auxiliary and service rooms, in particular a women's and men's clothing replacement room, with toilets and toilets, a massage room, a medical room.

Various large sports pavilions are also available, and the ulama rooms system includes several gyms, swimming pools, water jumpers and others. The quality of such in

¹ Turayev X. A. et al. YIG'MA BIRLIK CHIZMALARINI O'QISHDA TALABALARNING FAZOVIY TASAVVURINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA

OID ILMIY VA METODIK TAVSIYALAR //Молодой исследователь: вызовы и перспективы. – 2018. – С. 242-246.

pavilion numbers sports training will be improved and there will be an opportunity to use the building and the stadium more efficiently.²

Universal gyms as a result of the development of sports and throughout the year, training on sports (gymnastics, light and weightlifting, boxing, Sports Games, cycling, etc.), training on skates, training on the basis of the requirements for the conduct of demonstration work, appeared and became widespread (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Salsal gyms have their Sports Arena, a Tribune designed for 10-15 thousand spectators, as well as training halls and show-rooms serving the audience and in the following order: entrance (for the audience) rooms, wardrobes, buffets, kiosks and toilets for the audience; rooms for athletes-with wardrobe, changing clothes, shower and toilet, massage, medical part, judges, rest rooms, buffets, others; administrative-economic-management, economic department, cash desks, protection room, Training Department, post-Telegraph, etc.; auxiliary rooms — for refrigeration appliances, heating, ventilation, transformer substation, workshops, etc. will consist (Figure 2).

On the basis of the architectural-plan and spatial composition of this building lies a rectangular structure, whose volume dimensions are simple and clearly expressed from the outside. The building has a sports arena with dimensions of 30x61 m, a Tribune with 15000 seats, a training and training gym and a service room for athletes and spectators. The sports arena is used for various purposes. It will host competitions in surfing, Gymnastics and boxing, training sessions, or figure skating demonstrations on artificial ice. The capacity of the audience reaches 17500 people with the formation of folding seats for the audience in boxing (Figure 3).

² Тураев Х. А. АЙЛАНИШ СИРТЛАРИНИНГ СОЯЛАРИНИ ЯСАШ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ФАЗОВИЙ ТАСАВВУРИ ВА

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Figure 3

Figure 4

The hall is equipped with all kinds of modern jigsaws for athletes and spectators.

The filling and evacuation of the stands is carried out with the help of a vestibule surrounding the Hall on the first floor, and on the second floor with the help of huts. In the stands, lean, side-less seats were raised. The seat has a width of 40 cm for one viewer, the distance between the cross-passageways is up to 35-50 CM. The depth of the watch rows is 75 cm. In the sections between the corridors,

the audience is located from 800 to 1150 people. Eni 1,5 m corresponds to the evacuation hatch (every 650 people) 1 longitudinal meter of the evacuation passage. The height of the hall is 18 meters, the building capacity is 248000 m³. The construction of the

building consists of a carcass, a 6x6m constructive grate, a folding reinforced concrete. The closing range of the hall is 78 m, performed on the basis of metal farms.³

The plan of the gym in Madrid is rectangular, the main entrance is located in the front part of the facade (Figure 4).

Unlike the previous schemes, the main part of the hall is attached here with two parts that push forward and where additional rooms are located. The audience is located in tribunes in the form of a three-tier theater. It is permissible to mention the peculiarity of the closing of the Hall, the such is interconnected in the form of a mirror two-joint shell in the direction of the closing longitudinal.

References:

1. H.M.Ubaydullayev va boshqalar. "Turar joy va jamoat binolarini loyihalashning tipologik asoslari".-T.: "Vorish-nashriyot". 2009-y.
2. M.Xalimov. "Chizmachilik".-T.: "TDPU ruzografi". 2013-y.
3. I.Rahmonov, A.Valiyev. "Chizmachilik".-T.: "Vorish-nashriyot". 2011-y.
4. I.Rahmonov va boshqalar. "Chizmachilik".-T.: "Vorish-nashriyot". 2016-y.

³ Turayev X. A. et al. METHODOICAL RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE THEME OF FORTY

IN DRAWING LESSONS GRAPHICALLY //Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 264-268.